

OIKONET A global multidisciplinary network on housing research and learning

Deliverable 6.2

Feedback on the evaluations from the events

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Work Programme Description	<p>The reports will provide some interpretations and feedbacks to the data collected in the evaluation activities of the events planned in the respective WPs (participatory actions, international workshops, exhibitions), providing also, where necessary, some suggestions to improve the effectiveness of future events.</p> <p>The evaluation of the different types of events will be performed through questionnaires that will be distributed to the participants during each event. Questionnaire submission, data collection and analysis will be done by the promoter of any single event or by the corresponding work package leader. The evaluation will focus on different aspects of the event, including organizational aspects, participants' satisfaction, and their perception of its effectiveness and impact onto local communities.</p>				
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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report briefly presents and discusses the results of the evaluation of events that took place during the whole OIKONET project. 18 sub-network meetings, three annual general meetings and three international conferences have been evaluated to understand the effectiveness of these events in reaching the project outcomes and their impact on stakeholders. Evaluations have been performed through online questionnaires that were submitted to events' participants after the events; only in the case of the three International Conferences, paper questionnaires have been handed in to participants at the end of the event. Response rates have been generally high; only in one case (fourth meeting of WP3), response rate fell under 50% (30%, 3 participants out of 10, however representing 50% of participating institutions).

The main findings of these evaluations can be summarized as follows:

Sub-network meetings:

- Generally speaking, sub-network meetings were considered **useful and successful**. Participants' expectations have usually been met at a high degree. It emerged that it was very **important for partners to meet in person**, as this allowed partners to create a real network.
- Identifying forms of **communication and collaboration** was a crucial issue in the project: it is important that partners regularly communicate also in between meetings. It emerged also the importance of **making meetings interactive and dynamic** in order to foster active participation of all partners: in some cases this happened, in other cases some respondents complained because meetings were too much presentation-oriented.
- In some cases, it emerged that **not all partners were equally engaged and active**: it was suggested that during the meeting specific tasks were defined for everyone as well as expected outputs and deadlines.

General meetings:

- Also the general meetings were considered **very useful, productive, effective and inspiring**. In the first meeting, participants particularly appreciated the **inspiring working atmosphere**. The **importance of meeting face-to-face** all the project members at least once per year was also stressed.
- Expectations mainly regarded the possibility to **get to know each other and create networks, interact and exchange ideas** in order to find ways of collaborating, also with members of different WPs, **get updates on the status of the project and agree on its future activities**. **Expectations were generally met at a high degree**, although in some cases some participants would have appreciated **more discussions to define future project activities**.
- Also in the general meetings, participants stressed the importance of **enhancing communications and collaborations** between partners, both during and in-between meetings.

International conferences:

- In all conferences, participants **appreciated the selection of topics and the invited keynote speakers**, and found most presentations interesting and useful. In some cases, **more attention could have been dedicated to the quality of presentations**.
- The conference **schedule changed in the three editions and received different feedbacks**: while **in the first two conferences the schedule was found to be too tight**, thus making it difficult for participants to concentrate, **in the last conference the compact 1-day program with parallel sessions was generally appreciated**.

- Participants agreed that the all the conferences increased their knowledge about the project, provided many **opportunities for networking**, and **invoked a change in their professional practices**.
- Especially in the first two conferences, participants would have **expected to meet more persons external to the project**, while almost all participants were project partners. This changed in the **third conference, which was attended by a higher number of external participants**.

As regards the **organizational aspects**, participants were generally **very satisfied** with the organization and the guidance of all meetings and of the three conferences.

2 INTRODUCTION

2.1 Purpose and target group

According to the project description, the reports of Deliverable 6.2 “will provide some interpretations and feedbacks to the data collected in the evaluation activities of the events planned in the respective WPs (participatory actions, international workshops, exhibitions), providing also, where necessary, some suggestions to improve the effectiveness of future events”.

During the 36 months of the OIKONET project, 18 sub-network meetings, three annual general meetings and three international conferences have been evaluated. To do so, several surveys have been created and sent or handed in to the respective target groups, according to the evaluation plan that was developed as Deliverable 6.1.

The table below lists the events that took place during the project and the way they were evaluated. Evaluation wanted to assess the event’s effectiveness in reaching the project outcomes, their impact on stakeholders and the satisfaction of its participants.

Event	When	Evaluation	Response Rate	
Sub-network meetings – Round 1	WP2 – Preston	19.12.2013	Online Survey	61.5% (8 out of 13)
	WP3 – Barcelona	07.02.2014	Online Survey	100% (8 out of 8)
	WP4 – Barcelona	10.01.2014	Online Survey	75% (15 out of 20)
Sub-network meetings – Round 2	WP2 – Ljubljana	16-17.06.2014	Online Survey	83.3% (10 out of 12)
	WP3 – Rimini	27.06.2014	Online Survey	80% (8 out of 10)
	WP4 – Lisbon	16-18.07.2014	Online Survey	50% (12 out of 24)
General Meeting	Barcelona	25-27.09.2014	Online Survey	69% (29 out of 42)
1 st International Conference	Barcelona	25-26.09.2014	Paper Survey	79.1% (34 out of 43)
Sub-network meetings – Round 3	WP2 – Budapest	12-13.12.2014	Online Survey	60% (9 out of 15)
	WP3 – Bratislava	27.02.2015	Online Survey	63.6% (7 out of 11)
	WP4 – Istanbul	30.01.2015	Online Survey	77.8% (14 out of 18)
Sub-network meetings – Round 4	WP2 – Rotterdam	05.06.2015	Online Survey	61.5% (8 out of 13)
	WP3 – Tirana	19.06.2015	Online Survey	30% (3 out of 10)
	WP4 – Cottbus	31.05-03.06.2015	Online Survey	68.2% (15 out of 22)
2 nd General Meeting	Bratislava	24-26.09.2015	Online Survey	65.7% (23 out of 35)
2 nd International Conference	Bratislava	25.09.2015	Paper Survey	56.3% (27 out of 48)
Sub-network meetings – Round 5	WP2 – Zagreb	20.11.2015	Online Survey	61.5% (8 out of 13)
	WP3 – Skopje	18.12.2015	Online Survey	All 4 institutions
	WP4 – Brussels	22-23.01.2016	Online Survey	71.4% (15 out of 21)
Sub-network meetings – Round 6	WP2 – Riga	22.04.2016	Online Survey	5 out of 6 institutions
	WP3 – Barcelona	04.03.2016	Online Survey	85.7% (6 out of 7)
	WP4 – Belgrade	05-09.06.2016	Online Survey	11 out of 17 institutions
3 rd General Meeting	Manchester	22.09.2016	--	--
3 rd International Conference	Manchester	23.09.2016	Paper Survey	57.6% (34 out of 59)

In the second half of the project, in some cases, the response rate has been calculated on the basis of the institutions represented rather than on the individuals who attended the meeting. As a matter of fact, most often, when more than one person per institution attended a meeting (general meetings or sub-network meetings), the survey was completed by only one of them as a representative of the institution.

Different target groups have been involved in the evaluation activities:

- Sub-network meetings and general meetings: all project partners who participated in the meetings.
- International conferences: all project partners who attended the conference, invited external speakers, external participants in the conference.

2.2 Contribution of partners

As leader of WP6 Quality Assurance, USI has been responsible for the creation and the publication of the evaluation questionnaires, for the analysis of the received feedbacks, and for the creation of the single reports for each event and of this report that summarizes the results of the abovementioned evaluation activities.

As collaborator in WP6, Paul Riddy has collaborated in the creation of the questionnaires.

Karim Hadjri, as leader of WP2, and Leandro Madrazo, as leader of WP3 and WP4, have collaborated in the adaptation of the evaluation questionnaires to the agenda of the single sub-network meetings, and in the diffusion of the questionnaires among the respective WP partners.

2.3 Relations to other activities in the project

As the results of the evaluation activities summarized in this document deal with different kind of events that are included in WP2 Housing Research, WP3 Community Participation, WP4 Pedagogical Activities and WP7 Dissemination, this report concerns specifically the leaders of those WPs; however, as all project members were involved in the abovementioned events, the overall OIKONET project and project members can be concerned by this report.

2.4 Abbreviations

- WP stands for **Work Package**.

3 SUB-NETWORK MEETINGS

During the 36 months of OIKONET, the members of the three project's sub-networks (WP2 – Housing Research, WP3 – Community Participation, and WP4 – Pedagogical Activities) came together six times in order to discuss the progress of the work and to define future steps.

3.1 Meeting expectations

In the meetings of the **1st round**, participants mainly expected to **get to know** each other, to learn about the **OIKONET project** and the **respective WPs**, to find **collaborations** with other WP members and to define tasks for everyone. **WP4 participants** also expected to **solve their communication problems**, which made collaboration in the design of learning activities very difficult.

In the meetings of the **2nd round**, participants mainly expected to **consolidate the group**, to understand the work progresses, to start identifying **collaborations between WPs** and to plan future activities.

In the meetings of the **3rd round**, participants mainly expected to **get updates on the project and on the sub-network's activities**, to **plan and coordinate future activities**, and to **strengthen collaboration with other WPs**. The importance of meeting colleagues in person was also mentioned.

In the third round of meetings, some partners in WP2 and WP3 stressed the fact that **not all partners were equally engaged and active** during the meeting and in the project.

In the meetings of the **4th round**, participants mainly expected to **share with other partners their activities** in the past months and to **be updated** by them (especially, in WP4), to better **define collaborations** with other partners, to **get updates on the project's and sub-network's activities**, and to **plan and coordinate future activities**, especially the future workshops for WP4, and the Reader and the Book for WP2.

Similar expectations emerged also in the meetings of the **5th round**, with a sharp **focus on the final part of the project**: to get a clear view and to plan the next steps, the final activities and the deliverables for the final year of the project. Also in these meetings, some expectations about **specific topics and activities** were mentioned: the Reader, the OIKOPEDIA and the book for WP2, the Belgrade workshop and the MOOC for WP4.

In the **last round** of meetings, expectations regarded mainly the **exact definition of the last activities to be done in the project**: completion of ongoing tasks, clarification of final steps, deadlines, administrative issues, deliverables, and so on.

For most participants **expectations were met to a high degree**. After the second round of meetings roles and tasks started to be clearer. A warm and friendly atmosphere fostered collaboration among participants. The only complaint was that after the second WP4 meeting, many partners were still **not clear about the MOOC to be developed**. They would have liked to spend more time on this topic in order to understand how to start implementing it.

In the second half of the project, the **discussions were fruitful** and helped **participants be more aware of their tasks and of the next steps of the project**. A few complaints emerged in some meetings: in one case, about the lack of conclusions and of an action plan at the end of the meeting; in another case about the fact that not all partners did their homework before the meeting and/or attended it; finally, according to some participants, in some cases time constraints prevented the meeting to be fruitful. It is worth noting that in some cases, participants gave opposite feedbacks about the same meeting: while one participant found the meeting fruitful and successful, another one found it useless.

3.2 Meeting sessions

3.2.1 First 18 months

Participants stressed the **importance of preparatory activities** (individual or in small groups) in order to start thinking beforehand about the topics to be discussed and, this way, to make the meeting more effective. The use of **presentation templates** was very much appreciated as it led towards more focused and comparable outputs. Some suggested to keep the partners' presentations shorter, more structured and more focused. Well-designed templates and the observance of assigned speaking times can help achieve this in future meetings.

During the first round of meetings, the detailed presentation of the OIKONET project and of respective WPs was fundamental to create a **common understanding** of the project. During the second and third rounds, topics that were more specific to each WP were discussed (e.g. WP2: OIKOPEDIA, Research Matrix; WP3: Rimini Community Action; WP4: Design of Learning Activities, MOOCs). WP4 members would have liked to **discuss the MOOC in more detail** in the second meeting: its concept was still vague to many of them; this request was not repeated in the feedback from the third meeting, thus showing that the **work on the OIKONET MOOC proceeded well** after the second meeting and that **information about it were made more clear** by then. WP3 members very much appreciated the **involvement of Rimini stakeholders**, and their willingness to explain their experience.

The **interactive sessions**, where partners discussed a topic in smaller groups, were considered a good way to get **people engaged** and to **learn more about each other**. They were particularly useful to identify collaboration strategies and exchange ideas. Some members suggested to **plan** these sessions **better**, make them **more focused** and to **group people by common interests/activities**. Especially in the third round of meetings, some partners would have preferred to have **more discussion sessions** and fewer presentations.

The concluding sessions provided a **good summary** of the meeting's progresses and of the future steps. Partners appreciated that during each meeting some time was dedicated to **project management** issues. In the third round of meetings, the **site visits after the meetings (Bratislava and Budapest) were also particularly appreciated**.

3.2.2 Second half of the project

Generally speaking, **the introduction sessions of all meetings have been highly appreciated**, because they usually provided an update and a general overview on the status and on the progresses of the project. Also **concluding sessions have received rates above average**, because they were useful to understand the future activities of the project and to distribute tasks and deadlines to partners. Furthermore, the **guided tours** that in some cases were organized in the cities where the meeting took place have been appreciated very much. Finally, some **specific activities** carried out during some meetings have received high scores from participants: the reporting about the Learning Spaces promoted in the Winter semester 2015/2016 and the presentation of the results of the usability test of the project web portal (meeting 5 of WP4), and the activity of commenting on Reader 2 and on the Oikopedia entries (meeting 6 of WP2).

In some cases participants expressed their dissatisfaction about a session or a meeting: in meeting 5 of WP2 meeting, one participant would have preferred to have **more discussions about contents and less about procedures**; in meetings 4 and 5 of WP4, some participants found that **some discussions were not very focused** and could not come to a conclusion, due to limited time and/or to the fact that too many people were involved; again, in the last meeting of WP4 one session got a negative score, because the discussion was nervous and the atmosphere was tense, so participants found the session difficult, uncomfortable and confusing.

Finally, some critical comments have been expressed also about some specific project activities, such as dissemination activities, the status of the work about the MOOC and about the book, and about the participatory action in Bratislava. In those cases, however, participants were expressing their worries about the status of these activities at that given time rather than their negative remarks about the meetings or the sessions themselves.

3.3 Use of on-line tools

In the questionnaire of the **first round of meetings**, a couple of questions were asked about the use of communication tools in the project, to gather possible suggestions from partners at the very beginning of the project. After some initial difficulties (e.g. Dropbox account not working), most partners got used to the main tools used for communication and collaboration (Dropbox, e-mail, Google Docs, website) and consider them **useful** for the project's activities. They would appreciate **regular updates** about what is going on, for example through RSS feeds on the OIKONET website, or by sending out short briefings on a regular basis. A **quick guide** on the used tools and their correct application in the project would facilitate their use. It might be useful to include **tools that favour collaboration in small groups** (e.g. chats, forums). Most of these actions have been taken in the first year of the project.

It emerged that several users were **not clear about how the OIKODOMOS Workspaces work** both from a technical and conceptual point of view. A practical demonstration during a WP4 meeting would have been useful. Despite the initial problems, it is important that teachers actively use the platform and learn how to use it properly. Also in this case, some tutorials were shared among partners at the beginning of the project.

3.4 Communication & collaboration between WPs

After the second round of meetings the importance of **collaborating** not only within each WP but also **with other WPs** emerged. A first step towards this integration of the different WPs was involving WP4 members in the research activities, participating in the construction of the research matrix. However, more should be done to foster this integration: WP2 or WP3 participants could be involved in the preparation of learning spaces in collaboration with WP4 members, and housing research methodologies could be explored through a workshop/graduate course in an interdisciplinary way involving academia and community participation.

3.5 Overall meeting evaluation

3.5.1 First 18 months

Overall, participants judged the meetings of the first 18 months positively. The meetings were considered very **productive**, focused and created **tangible outcomes** with the **active participation** of most members. The willingness and commitment of the partners to collaborate and carry out tasks was appreciated. **Communication** among partners was evaluated as open and constructive, in spite of the difficulties, and as a result members started to **feel being part of a network**. Participants stressed the **importance of working together even stronger** and of fostering collaboration through exercises, brainstorming and discussion sessions during the meetings. The meetings were guided very skilfully towards productive solutions and were organized very well.

3.5.2 Second half of the project

Also in the second part of the project, the **general satisfaction** of participants with the sub-network meeting was **high**: only one meeting (meeting 4 of WP2) received an overall evaluation under 7/10 (6.88), all other meetings received a rate ranging from 7.4 to 8.8.

In the comments, participants reported that they found **the meetings productive**, expressed their **appreciation for the management**, and, especially in the last rounds of meetings, their **gratitude and satisfaction for participating in the project** and achieving so many results.

The following chart presents the overall meeting scores for each sub-network meeting (in red the sub-network meetings of WP2, in blue those of WP3, in green the meetings of WP4):

4 GENERAL MEETINGS

Three general meetings took place during the OIKONET project, always in conjunction with the international conferences:

- 1st general meeting, in Barcelona, on 25th and 27th September 2014
- 2nd general meeting, in Bratislava, on 24th and 26th September 2015
- 3rd general meeting, in Manchester, on 22nd September 2016.

4.1 First General Meeting (Barcelona)

The general meeting in Barcelona took place on September 25th / 27th, one year after the project's kick-off. The meeting was split into two sessions: a morning session on September 25th, dedicated to present the work carried by each subnetwork and to do a collaborative activity in groups; and a morning session on September 27th, dedicated to explain the financial management procedures of the project. It was the first time that all project partners (from all three sub-networks) came together. It thus allowed participants to get an overview of the whole project and the single activities of each sub-network.

The meeting was very useful and productive and provided many interesting inputs and networking opportunities. Respondents particularly appreciated the nice and inspiring atmosphere and for many of them it was fundamental to meet face-to-face the members of all sub-networks in order to start identifying potential collaborations.

4.1.1 Expectations

As it was the first time all partners met, one of the major expectations was to **get to know each other, interact and exchange ideas** in order to find ways of collaborating. Learning about the **progress of the work done** by the different WPs was another major expectation. Some expected to get more information on the project itself and to clarify issues linked to the financial management. For many it was fundamental to **define** the next steps and the direction **where the project is heading**.

For a majority of respondents these expectations have been met to a high extent and they feel more like being part of a network now. However, for some the **planning of future activities** and the **definition of where the project is heading** was **not satisfying**. More time should be dedicated to discuss these aspects.

4.1.2 Meeting sessions

The **presentations of the work done by each sub-network** were **well articulated** and comprehensive, and allowed to make the project and the work of each sub-network clearer.

The **group activity**, where partners had to **identify cross-WP collaborations**, was a good exercise, which allowed actively involving all the members. However, there was **not enough time** to elaborate concrete collaborations. The activity might have been more fruitful at a later stage of the meeting, when partners already got to know each other. **Group composition was not ideal**, as there was often a majority of members from one WP.

Even though the session about **project management** was not very interesting, it was fundamental to better understand the project's administrative and financial aspects. However, some respondents pointed out that these issues should not have the overhand in meetings.

Respondents thought that **more time and attention** should have been dedicated to **evaluation, dissemination and exploitation activities**. A lot of information was provided in a very short time, so that it was difficult to get a full understanding of the information provided.

4.1.3 Suggestions on how to improve the work of the network

- **Define** specific tasks for each partner and ensure that they are implemented in time.
- Identify ways of **cooperation** between the three WPs.
- **Exchange** and **keep each other informed** about other partners' and WPs' activities.
- **Decide and define** as a whole group **where the project is heading** and how to best bridge the different professional backgrounds.
- Schedule tasks in which students are involved early enough.

An **urgent need for enhanced communication and exchange** between partners (during and after meetings) emerged.

4.1.4 Suggestions for future meetings

- Finding a way to **actively engage everyone** through group sessions, informal discussions, round tables, and by introducing some discussion stimulating controversies on housing.
- Organizing a **site visit related to local housing developments** or other selected topics in each city where the meetings take place.
- Inviting representatives from the one sub-network to participate in the meetings of other sub-networks
- Giving some time to each WP to meet also during the general meeting.

4.2 Second General Meeting (Bratislava)

The second general meeting of the OIKONET project was held in Bratislava in conjunction with the second International Conference. Also in this case, the meeting was split into two parts, one before, one after the conference. The first part of the meeting was focused mainly on giving updates on the status of the different project work packages and on the issue of exploitation (WP8), whereas the second day of the meeting was dedicated mainly to the learning activities (WP4).

4.2.1 Expectations

Participants' expectations for the 2nd general meeting can be grouped in four main categories:

- **Networking.**
- Information and discussion about the **status of the project**: single WPs and connections among different WPs.
- **Next steps in the project**: tasks and collaborations for the next/last months of the project.
- **Future of the project and of the consortium.**

For a majority of respondents these expectations were met to a high extent: they found the meeting good and positive, and were satisfied with the big advances in the project. For some participants, however, expectations were met only partially: for one of them, the **planning of the future collaboration activities was not yet clear**. Finally, some participants complained about the fact that **some partners did not attend the meeting**.

4.2.2 Meeting sessions

The meeting was **highly appreciated** by participants: it was judged as **productive, inspiring, effective, well organized, with a clear agenda and relevant discussions**. **All the sessions** of the Bratislava meeting received **positive feedbacks**: the presentations of the opening session were clear, well-structured and to the point; the second session was important to foster collaborations among

different WPs. Two sessions received particularly high scores: the **activities for exploitation (WP8)**, which was evaluated very useful, important, productive, and well-designed; and the **presentation of the procedure for the usability test of the web portal (WP6)**, which provided clear and excellent instructions about the procedure to follow.

Some remarks were advanced about the fact that **some discussions did not come to a clear conclusion** (e.g., about the book plan and about the final conference), that **some deadlines were very onerous**, and that **too much material** was sent for the preparation of the meeting.

4.2.3 Suggestions on how to improve the work of the network

A few suggestions were proposed by participants to improve the future works of the project:

- **All partners must be engaged** and responsible for their respective tasks.
- **More publications** in listed journals are needed.
- It is necessary to insist on **further collaboration between partners** in this year's courses.
- It is important to have some **feedback from the partners of WP3 and WP4 about the Oikopedia entries**.

4.2.4 Suggestions for future meetings

Finally, a few suggestions were proposed by participants for the future project's general meetings:

- The meeting could be more flexible.
- Keep to time.
- Keep presentations shorter.
- Create groups with similar interest and concepts.

4.3 Third General Meeting (Manchester)

The third general meeting of the OIKONET project was held in Manchester in conjunction with the third International Conference. The meeting took place in the afternoon before the conference; the focus of the meeting was on the reflection about the work done in the project, on the presentation of the results achieved in the project as a whole and in each WP, on the identification of the missing outputs and of responsibilities, and on the procedures to follow to complete the project and the corresponding deadlines.

This General Meeting was not assessed through an online survey like the previous ones, because during the meeting an activity of general evaluation of the project and of its achievements was carried out, guided by the leaders of WP6. The findings that emerged from this session are presented in D6.5 (Final Quality Report).

5 INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCES

A series of three international conferences on “Global dwelling” were organized during the OIKONET project as part of the dissemination activities planned in WP7:

- 1st OIKONET International Conference, “**Research, Education, Community Participation**”, September 25-26, 2014, in Barcelona, attended by **43 participants**.
- 2nd OIKONET International Conference, “**Housing regeneration strategies**”, September 25th, 2015, in Bratislava, attended by **48 participants**.
- 3rd OIKONET International Conference, “**Sustainability – Design - Participation**”, September 23rd, 2016, in Manchester, attended by **59 participants**.

All three conferences were evaluated by getting the participants’ feedbacks through a paper questionnaire that was distributed at the end of the conferences.

5.1 First International Conference (Barcelona)

The first OIKONET international conference on the topic “Global dwelling” took place in Barcelona on 25-26 September 2014, organized by the School of Architecture La Salle. Its goal was to explore the global condition of contemporary housing in a multidisciplinary way that encompasses architecture, urban planning, sociology, economics and housing policy.

This first conference was addressed mostly to OIKONET partners, who presented their work to the other participants. Because of this, some respondents did not understand the difference between the international conference and the general meeting.

5.1.1 Organizational aspects

Respondents were very satisfied with the organization of the conference. It was easy to find information on the conference thanks to the many digital media that have been used to promote the event. Respondents appreciated the **selection of topics** and **keynote speakers**, the involvement of experts from various research fields, and the **open and friendly atmosphere** during the conference. The project coordinator was praised for the excellent governance of the whole project and for the organization of the conference.

The main complaints were that many **presentations ran over time** causing the cancellation of panel discussions and making the days very long; the session chairs should be in charge of guaranteeing that each speaker respects the time assigned to him/her.

5.1.2 Conference sessions

Both **keynotes** provided **interesting insights**. Claire-Lévy Vroelant’s speech got very diverse evaluations: some liked it very much, whereas others did not like it at all. Respondents **missed a visual presentation** (e.g. PowerPoint) without which it was difficult to follow her discourse. Ekim Tan’s presentation was appreciated by most respondents for both the topic and the way it was presented. Respondents suggested **including the keynote presentations in the proceedings**.

As regards the **presentations** in the different conference sessions, respondents considered most of them as very **informative, interesting and important to develop a common understanding** of the OIKONET topics. However, as some presentation issues emerged (e.g. reading from slides, language proficiency, time limits), some pointed out the importance of learning **how to communicate in an informative and entertaining way**, mentioning Nicolai Steinø’s presentation as a very good example. Many respondents expected more concrete conclusions. During the closing session a

general wrap-up would have been useful to clearly define the gained insights. Although a rich final panel session was organized, some participants would have liked to have panels for each conference session, as it was originally planned. A **better time-keeping** would have allowed more time for discussions.

Posters were placed well in order to look at them during coffee breaks. However, some respondents would have liked some time dedicated to **present and discuss** the posters. Some suggested placing the posters in a more public place so to make them visible also to others.

5.1.3 Conference outcomes

Participants agree that the conference **increased their knowledge** about the OIKONET project and that they learned about the work done by the other sub-networks. One of the strong points of the conference was certainly the fact that it provided many **opportunities for networking**. Respondents got to know their colleagues working in other sub-networks, managed to exchange ideas with them and to establish contacts among each other and even with the keynote speakers.

Most respondents answered that the conference **invoked a change in their teaching, research or work practices**. They plan to integrate the presented tools (e.g. OIKODOMOS – OIKOPEDIA), approaches and resources. Furthermore, they would like to include the use of digital tools and start **working with smaller groups of students**. Many would like to improve their way of presenting, following the examples given by Nicolai Steinø and Ekim Tan.

5.1.4 Suggestions for future conferences

Less and shorter presentations should be planned, in order to leave more time for discussions and networking. It was a pity that the panel discussions for sessions 1 and 2 did not take place because of lack of time. The schedule was perceived as being too dense and **time keeping was not handled well**. More attention should be paid to the **way the ideas are presented** (e.g., avoid reading, structure ideas, prepare speeches, prepare clear and appealing slides).

Respondents would have appreciated **more interactive activities**, such as round tables in between the sessions in order to make the conference more dynamic. An alternative would be to include a **field trip** to a scientifically interesting site in the city where the conference is held.

Meeting the partners of all WPs and being able to exchange ideas with each other allowed everyone to get a better picture of the whole project and of who is doing what.

Some respondents would have preferred to **open the conference also to non-OIKONET participants**.

5.2 Second International Conference (Bratislava)

The second OIKONET International Conference of the series on “Global Dwelling” was held in Bratislava (Slovakia) on September 25th, 2015, and focused on “Housing Regeneration Strategies”.

Also this second conference was attended mainly by OIKONET project partners, like the first one: only 5 of the respondents to the evaluation questionnaire (18.5%) were external to the project.

5.2.1 Organizational aspects

The **organization** of the conference was **highly appreciated** by all participants. For most of them it was also **easy to find information** about the conference. The **conference program** was also found **interesting**, as it provided a range of particular topics forming together a strong theme. The **topic** of the conference was also the reason that **attracted the external participants** to attend it.

A few complaints about organizational aspects were also advanced: as regards the infrastructure, **acoustics** in the room was **not very good**, and there were some problems with microphones; **schedule**

problems were also mentioned: shorter presentations would have been preferred.

5.2.2 Conference sessions

The **keynote speech by Aseem Inam** was **particularly appreciated**, also because it generated an **interesting discussion** afterwards. The keynote by **Richard Hayward** was generally appreciated, too, but for some participants it was **not easy to understand him**, as he was speaking too fast, grumbling sometimes, and not looking at the public. Also the **panel session and the other discussion sessions were highly appreciated**, although some participants found that UK was overrepresented in the panel discussion.

As regards the **presentations**, some participants found that their **quality was very different**: some of them were very good, some others were dull. Furthermore, some respondents found some presentations out of topic, while other respondents would have preferred a wider variety of topics in the presentations.

Also the **poster exhibition** was generally **appreciated**; one participant would have preferred to have a separate session to present the posters.

5.2.3 Conference outcomes

Like in the first conference in Barcelona, also in this second conference the **networking opportunities** were considered as one of the strong points of the conference: almost all participants found that the conference provided good opportunities for networking; in addition, **networking and interactions with colleagues** were mentioned by some respondents as the most appreciated aspect of the conference.

The conference was also useful to **increase the knowledge about the OIKONET project**, as reported by two thirds of respondents.

Finally, for several respondents **the participation to the conference invoked a change in their practices** (teaching, research, professional): for some of them, this could mean including the educational practices that were discussed or the ideas, concepts, topics and approaches that were presented; for others, it could be a change in the way of presenting their works to students.

5.2.4 Suggestions for next conferences

The **promotion** of the conference could be improved by involving and contacting established relevant networks in the field of housing studies, such as AHRA, ENHR, EEAE, ACE.

More debates, questions and discussions could be encouraged during the conference. Also the selection of presentations could be improved, trying to **open much more the conference to external speakers and participants**.

5.3 Third International Conference (Manchester)

The third OIKONET International Conference of the series on “Global Dwelling” was held in Manchester (United Kingdom) on September 23rd, 2016, and focused on “Sustainability – Design - Participation”.

In the third conference a higher participation of delegated who were not project partners could be noticed: 10 respondents to the evaluation questionnaire (29.4%) were external to the project.

5.3.1 Organizational aspects

Also in the third international conference, the **organization** was **highly appreciated** by most participants. The **1-day compact conference structure was also appreciated**, as it encouraged proximity and networking among participants. The **conference program** was also found **fascinating**

and stimulating, as it provided a **multidisciplinary approach** resulting in a great mix of presentations that touched different aspects of housing research. The **topic** of the conference was also the main reason that **attracted some external participants** to attend it. For most of the participants it was also **easy to find information** about the conference.

A few complaints about organizational aspects were also advanced: as regards the infrastructure, some respondents found that **rooms were not adequate**, having some problems with temperature and not enough seats for lunch; **schedule problems** were also mentioned: some respondents did not appreciate the parallel sessions, as they made it impossible to attend some presentations, also because of problems with timing.

5.3.2 Conference sessions

The **keynote speech by Iván Tosics** was **very much appreciated**, because he was able to well explain complex issues, providing good and interesting examples and inspiring many participants.

The **panel session was also appreciated**, although some participants found that the summaries of the single parallel sessions were too long, and that more space could have been given to critical thoughts and discussions.

As regards the different **presentation sessions**, respondents had different opinions: some presentations and discussions were interesting, instructive, lively and productive, while others were not very good, too diverse and difficult to follow.

The **poster exhibition** did not get high rates, because the poster authors were not present to illustrate their work, and because there were only four posters.

5.3.3 Conference outcomes

Like in the two previous conferences, also in the third one the **networking opportunities** were considered as one of the strong points of the conference: almost all participants found that the conference provided good opportunities for networking; in addition, **the possibility to meet again with OIKONET colleagues** was explicitly mentioned by some respondents among the most appreciated aspects of the conference.

The conference was also useful to **increase the knowledge about the OIKONET project**, as reported by 70% of respondents.

Finally, for several respondents **the participation in the conference invoked a change in their practices** (teaching, research, professional), in terms of **new topics** to include in their teaching activities and of **new methodologies** to experiment in teaching and to include in research practices.

6 CONCLUSIONS

At the half of the project, six main issues emerged as particularly relevant from the evaluations of the events. We report here these issues, adding a comment on how the situation changed (or not) in the second half of the project.

- 1) **The importance of meeting in person:** both in the sub-network meetings and in the general meeting, it emerged that it was very important for partners to meet in person, in order to make first contacts and get to know each other, to better understand the project goals and to know what each sub-network is doing.

Second half of the project: meeting in person was considered as very important and was appreciated very much also in the second half of the project, although with different goals.

- 2) **Communication** is still an issue. It is important that partners **communicate** on a regular basis **also in between meetings** and that they keep each other informed on their activities. Exchanging online in smaller groups might be a feasible solution. Thanks to the **good atmosphere and open communication during meetings**, partners now feel more like being part of a network.

Second half of the project: after the communication tools to be used in the project were defined, **communication has been less and less an issue**. Some small groups working on specific activities have been formed (e.g., groups to run common learning activities in WP4), thus strengthening the feeling of being part of a network, as observed also by prof. Flora Samuel in her “OIKONET Final External Assessor Report” (see Deliverable 6.5 “Final Quality Report”).

- 3) **Collaboration:** identifying forms of collaborations within and among different WPs is a key aspect of the project. Thus, during the meetings it is important to actively foster collaboration among partners through exercises, brainstorming and discussion sessions. As it emerged that not all partners are equally engaged and active, it is also important to make meetings interactive and dynamic in order to **foster active participation of all partners**: short presentations by each partner, well-planned group sessions and the introduction of controversy stimulating discussions are ways to foster participation. In order to **facilitate collaborations among different WPs**, it was suggested that each sub-network could invite a representative of the other two WPs to attend their sub-network meetings and then report back to their own WP; this was done in the third round of sub-network meetings.

Second half of the project: although during the project meetings collaboration was fostered by proposing discussions and activities, **the problem of having some partners not fully engaged and active remained** also in the second half of the project, thus creating some complaints and dissatisfaction in some partners.

- 4) **Topics and structure of the international conference:** partners **appreciated the selection of topics and the keynote speakers**. Presentations were interesting and helpful in gaining a good understanding of the project; however, **more attention** should be paid **to how ideas are presented**. Fewer and shorter presentations and a better time-keeping would have left **more time for discussions and networking**. More activities such as round tables or a field trip should be included in between sessions to make the conference more varied.

Second half of the project: also in the second and third international conferences, the selected topics, the keynote speakers and the networking opportunities were highly appreciated. Furthermore, the fact that the last conference was attended by **more external participants** (i.e., other than partners) was also appreciated.

- 5) The **difference between international conference and general meeting was not clear** to all partners. As the two events took place during the same days, in the same place and with the same participants (mainly project members), for some it was difficult to distinguish them, feeling as if the two events were one single big event.

Second half of the project: this problem was not observed in the second half of the project, probably due to the experience and the knowledge gained during the project.

- 6) **Organizational aspects**: according to participants, all the meetings and the annual conference were **guided very skilfully and were well organized**. Several respondents suggested **organizing a site visit** related to local housing issues in each city where meetings or conferences take place; this was done in the third round of meetings of WP2 and WP3, and it was particularly appreciated.

Second half of the project: the organization of meetings and conferences was highly appreciated also in the second half of the project. The site visits became a sort of “tradition” in the OIKONET meetings and conferences.